

Title. Does ultrasound-scored synovitis depend on the pharmacokinetics of subcutaneous anti-TNF agents in patients with rheumatoid arthritis?

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Short title. Anti-TNF pharmacokinetics in Doppler US synovitis

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ABSTRACT

Objective. To investigate the influence of the pharmacokinetics of subcutaneous anti-Tumour Necrosis Factor (anti-TNF) agents on the grade of ultrasound (US)-detected synovitis in RA patients.

Methods. Fifty RA patients were prospectively recruited from the Biologic Therapy Unit of our hospital. Inclusion criteria were; being in treatment with subcutaneous anti-TNF agents and having had neither changes in therapy nor local corticosteroid injections in the previous 3 months. Patients underwent clinical, laboratory [Disease Activity Score in 28 joints (DAS28) and Simplified Disease Activity Index (SDAI)] and US assessment at two time points, i.e., at peak plasma drug concentration and at trough plasma drug concentration. US assessments were performed blindly to the anti-TNF agent, the administration time, and the clinical and laboratory data. Twenty-eight joints were investigated for the presence and grade (0-3) of B-mode synovitis and synovial power Doppler signal. Global indices for B-mode synovitis (BSI) and Doppler synovitis (DSI) were calculated for 12 joints and for wrist-hand-ankle-foot joints. B-mode US remission was defined as a $BSI < 1$ and Doppler US remission as a $DSI < 1$.

Results. There were no significant differences between the clinical, laboratory and B-mode and Doppler US parameters at peak time and trough time ($p=0.132-0.986$). There were no significant differences between the proportion of patients with active disease and those in remission according to DAS28, SDAI, B-mode US, and Doppler US at peak time and trough time assessments ($p=0.070-1$).

Conclusion. Our results suggested that subcutaneous anti-TNF pharmacokinetics does not significantly influence US-scored synovitis in RA patients.

Key-words. Ultrasound, Doppler, synovitis, rheumatoid arthritis, pharmacokinetics

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease characterised by synovial inflammation that can severely damage joints (1). The principal objective of RA therapy is remission of the disease (2). The current treatment of RA consists of synthetic disease modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) and biologic DMARDs when remission or minimal disease activity is not achieved with the former.

Within the last decade, technological improvements in B-mode ultrasound (US) image resolution of musculoskeletal (MS) structures and Doppler mode sensitivity in detecting small-vessel blood flow have led to an increasingly important role of this imaging modality in the assessment and monitoring of patients with RA. MSUS is a routinely available, non-invasive, repeatable as many times as required at the time of consultation, and relatively inexpensive bedside technique with high patient acceptability. Synovitis can be evaluated in both B-mode (i.e. morphological aspect) and Doppler mode. Doppler technique is able to detect synovial flow, which is an indirect sign of inflammatory activity (3-7). B-mode US has widely demonstrated greater sensitivity than clinical assessment for detecting synovitis in RA target joints in patients with both clinically active and inactive disease (6, 8-16). In addition, US-detected subclinical synovitis, mainly Doppler-detected synovitis, has shown predictive value in relation to both radiographic damage progression in active and inactive RA patients (17-23) and disease flare or relapse in RA patients in clinical remission (12,21,24,25).

Many observational studies have shown responsiveness of B-mode and Doppler-detected synovitis in RA patients, most of them using biologic DMARDs as treatment (17,20,26-35). In addition, US-detected synovitis has been recently accepted as an OMERACT (Outcome Measures in Rheumatology)-endorsed secondary endpoint for

monitoring therapeutic response in clinical trials (36). However, the above published studies (17,20,26-35) have not taken into consideration the pharmacokinetic characteristics of the drug administered in their design. The objective of this study was to investigate whether the pharmacokinetics [i.e. time point of US assessment] of subcutaneous anti-Tumour Necrosis Factor (anti-TNF) agents influences the grade of US-detected synovitis in RA patients treated with these drugs.

METHODS

Fifty consecutive patients (31 women, 18 men) who fulfilled the American College of Rheumatology 1987 diagnostic criteria for RA (37) were prospectively recruited from the Biologic Therapy Unit of the Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón (Madrid, Spain). Inclusion criteria consisted of being in treatment with subcutaneous anti-TNF agents and having had neither changes in therapy including synthetic and biologic DMARDs, corticosteroid and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) nor local corticosteroid injections in the previous 3 months.

Patients underwent clinical, laboratory and US assessment at two time points, i.e., at peak (maximum) plasma drug concentration and at trough (lowest) plasma drug concentration. Peak time and trough time were established according to the technical specifications of the anti-TNF agents provided by the Spanish Health Authorities from the respective pharmaceutical laboratories. For each patient, these time points were randomly chosen from three consecutive administrations of the anti-TNF agent to keep the investigator who performed the Doppler US assessments (EN) blinded to the time point, i.e., either peak time or trough time. The two assessment time points (i.e. time to peak plasma drug concentration after drug administration and the day before the following drug administration) for each subcutaneous anti-TNF agent authorized for RA are shown in table 1.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the local ethics committee of the Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón (Madrid, Spain). Informed consent was obtained from all patients before study enrollment.

Clinical and laboratory assessment

Patient demographics and RA features, including presence of rheumatoid factor (RF) [nephelometry; >20 IU] and anti-citrullinated peptide antibodies (ACPAs) [second generation commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (Immunoscan RA; Euro-Diagnostica, Malmö, Sweden; >25 IU] and RA treatment were recorded at study entry.

Patients were assessed at both time points for disease activity according to the Disease Activity Score in 28 joints (DAS28) and the Simplified Disease Activity Index (SDAI) by the same investigator (MH). At each visit, 28 joints, including the left and right glenohumeral, elbow, and wrist joints, metacarpophalangeal (MCP) joints, proximal interphalangeal joints of the hands, and knee joints were assessed for tenderness and swelling. Tender joint counts and swollen joint counts were recorded. The patients and the clinical investigator rated the overall disease activity on a 10-cm visual analog scales (VAS) at each visit. Data on serum markers of inflammation [C-reactive protein (CRP) level; normal 0-0.5 mg/dL and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR); normal 10-20 mm/1st h] were obtained from laboratory tests performed on the day of each clinical and US evaluation. In addition, functional ability was assessed with a self-assessment Spanish version of the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ) (38).

Clinical remission was defined at both time point by DAS28 ($DAS28 < 2.6$) (39) and SDAI ($SDAI < 3.3$) criteria (40).

US assessment

Patients underwent US assessment at the two time points, on the day of the clinical assessments, by a rheumatologists highly experienced in MSUS (EN) who was blinded to the anti-TNF agent, the administration time of the anti-TNF agent (i.e. either peak time or trough time), and the clinical and laboratory data.

All US examinations were carried out in a dark room with temperature kept stable at 23°C. The patients rested for 15 mn in the waiting room before the US examinations. The patients were asked to avoid caffeine and alcohol intake, sport, and smoking for 8 hours before the US examinations. To reduce the possibility of bias, the patients were asked not to talk about their symptoms to the US examiner. The two US assessments of each patient were carried out at the same time in the morning with a maximum difference of 1 h.

The US examinations were performed with a real-time scanner (LOGIQ E9, GE Medical Systems Ultrasound and Primary Care Diagnostics, LLC, Wauwatosa, WI, USA) equipped with a multifrequency linear matrix array transducer (6-15 MHz). B-mode and PD machine settings were optimised before the study and standardised for the whole study. These settings were as follows: B-mode frequency of 11-15 MHz depending on the depth of the anatomic area, B-mode gain of 51 dB, dynamic range 57 dB, Doppler frequency of 7.5-10 MHz depending on the depth of the anatomic area, Doppler gain of 18 dB, low-wall filters, and pulse repetition frequency of 800 Hz.

The US assessment consisted of a systematic longitudinal and transverse B-mode and power Doppler (PD) examination, using a widely described standardised scanning technique (i.e. patient position and probe placement) (15,20,31), of bilateral elbow (anterior and posterior recesses), wrist (dorsal recess of radiocarpal, midcarpal and distal radioulnar joints), second through fifth MCP joints (dorsal recess), knee (suprapatellar and parapatellar recesses), ankle (anterior tibiotalar recess), and second

through fifth metatarsophalangeal (MTP) (dorsal recess) joints (total 28 joints). These joints were investigated for the presence of B-mode synovitis (i.e. either synovial hypertrophy or effusion) and synovial PD signal (i.e. Doppler synovitis). B-mode synovitis was defined as the presence of abnormal hypoechoic intra-articular material (31,41). We considered wrist synovitis or synovial PD signal positive if they were detected in the radiocarpal, midcarpal or distal radioulnar joints. At each scanned synovial recess, B-mode synovitis was scored semiquantitatively on a scale of 0-3 (0, absent; 1, mild; 2, moderate; 3, marked). Synovial PD signal was also scored on a semiquantitative scale of 0-3 (0, no synovial flow; 1, mild [≤ 3 PD signals]; 2, moderate [> 3 PD signals in less than half of the synovial area]; 3, marked [signals in more than half of the synovial area] (20,42). Each joint was scored for B-mode synovitis and synovial PD signal on a scale from 0 to 3. These scores corresponded to the maximum score for B-mode synovitis and synovial PD signal, respectively, obtained from any one of the synovial sites evaluated at each joint.

A global index for B-mode synovitis (BSI) (the sum of the B-mode synovitis scores obtained for each evaluated joint or joint region), the joint count for B-mode synovitis (BSC), a global index for Doppler synovitis (DSI) (the sum of synovial PD signal scores obtained for each evaluated joint or joint region), and the joint count for Doppler synovitis (DSC) were calculated for a 12-joint US scoring model (31) and a wrist-MCP-ankle-MTP US scoring model (15) for each patient at each assessment time point. The 12-joint US scoring model included bilateral elbow, wrist, second and third MCP joints, knee and ankle joints (31). The wrist-MCP-ankle-MTP US scoring model included 20 joints as follows: bilateral wrist, second through fifth MCP joints, ankle, and second through fifth MTP joints (15). B-mode US remission was defined as a BSI < 1 and Doppler US remission as a DSI < 1 .

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, version 15.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Quantitative variables were presented as the mean \pm SD and range. Qualitative variables were summarized as absolute and relative frequencies. Comparisons between quantitative variables at peak time and trough time were analysed using the Student t test for paired samples. Comparisons between proportions of patients at the two time points were analysed using the McNemar's test. P values less than 0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS

Demographic and RA features

Complete data were obtained for 49 patients. One patient missed the second assessment. The mean (SD, range) age of the patients was 55.3 (12.3, 22-80) years, the mean (SD, range) disease duration was 10.9 (7.9, 1-32) years, and the mean (SD, range) duration of treatment with the anti-TNF agent was 25.4 (15.4, 3-59) months. Thirty-six (73.5 %) patients were RF positive and 36 (73.5%) were ACPA positive.

Twenty (40.8%) patients were treated with etanercept, 19 (38.8%) were treated with adalimumab, 6 (12.2%) were treated with golimumab, and 4 (8.2%) were treated with certolizumab. Thirty-six (73.5 %) patients were taking synthetic DMARDs [30 (61.2%) patients were taking methotrexate and 6 (12.2%) were taking leflunomide]. Nine (18.4%) patients were taking prednisone and 2 (4.1%) were taking NSAIDs. There were neither changes in the treatment nor local corticosteroid injections in any patient during the study period.

Comparison between clinical, laboratory and US parameters between peak time and trough time assessments

Table 2 displays the values (i.e. mean, SD and range) of clinical, laboratory, and B-mode and Doppler US parameters at the two assessment time points and the differences [with 95% confidence interval (CI)] between these values at both time points. There were no significant differences between the clinical and laboratory parameters and the B-mode and Doppler US indices and joint counts for both the 12-joint scoring model and the wrist-MCP-ankle-MTP scoring model at peak time and trough time assessments (p=0.130-0.986).

There were no significant differences between the proportion of patients with active disease and those in remission according to DAS28, SDAI, B-mode US, and Doppler US at peak time and trough time assessments (p=0.070-1) (table 3).

Most patients showed either equal values or higher values of these variables at trough time assessment than at peak time assessment (table 4).

Representative US images of B-mode and Doppler synovitis are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

DISCUSSION

US-detected and scored synovitis by both B-mode and Doppler mode has been used in many studies on monitoring therapeutic response in RA patients (17,20,26-35). In addition to the interobserver and intraobserver variability inherent to US as a diagnostic imaging modality (43), there are a number of factors that can influence the detection and scoring of US synovitis. (44-50). These factors depend on the scanning technique (45,46), the machine (50) and the patient (44,47-49). Patient position (46) and probe pressure (45) at US examination, examination time (i.e. diurnal variation) (48), patient's skin temperature (47), and some drug such as systemic or intra-articular corticosteroids and NSAIDs (44,49) have shown a confounding effect on Doppler US-

scored synovitis. To the best of our knowledge, the potential influence of the pharmacokinetics of drugs on US synovitis has not been previously investigated.

We chose RA patients on anti-TNF therapy because most studies on B-mode and Doppler US monitoring of RA response have used biologic agents as therapeutic intervention (9,26-31,33). In addition, further RA clinical trials with biologic treatments are expected in which US will play a role as an endpoint. In particular we focused on subcutaneous anti-TNF to make the RA therapy sample as homogeneous as possible. We used two US scoring models [i.e.12-joint and wrist-hand-ankle-foot joints] for B-mode synovitis and Doppler synovitis that have shown high sensitivity in detecting clinical and subclinical synovitis as compared with a comprehensive US assessment in RA patients (15,31).

Although there was a tendency to find higher mean clinical, laboratory and B-mode and Doppler US values at trough time assessment than at peak time assessment and more patients showed higher values of these parameters at trough time assessment than at peak time assessment, these differences were not significant in our study. Given the capability of B-mode and Doppler US to detect synovitis in asymptomatic RA joints (9,19), one might expect that changes in plasmatic concentrations of anti-TNF between administration could influence the presence and/or grade of US-detected synovitis. However, this hypothesis was not confirmed in our study.

Some limitations in our study should be mentioned. The population size was not enough big to analyse separately the data for each anti-TNF. The concomitant treatment with synthetic DMARDs, corticosteroids and NSAIDs, although unchanged in the previous 3 months and during the study, was not standardised among patients because of the observational design of the study. In addition, the duration of treatment with the anti-TNF agent varied from a few months to nearly five years while the first year of

treatment with an anti-TNF agent is the most common scenario in clinical trials on drug efficacy.

In conclusion, our results suggested that subcutaneous anti-TNF pharmacokinetics does not significantly influence the score of B-mode and Doppler US synovitis in RA patients.

Key messages

B-mode and Doppler US-scored synovitis has been used to monitor therapeutic response in RA patients.

A number of factors that can influence the detection and scoring of US synovitis.

Anti-TNF pharmacokinetics did not influence the score of B-mode and Doppler synovitis in RA patients.

Conflict of interest statement

Esperanza Naredo has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Pfizer, UCB, General Electric Healthcare, and Esaote. Esperanza Naredo has received research funding from UCB and MSD.

Indalecio Monteagudo Sáez has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Pfizer, UCB.

Juan Carlos Nieto-González has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Pfizer, MSD.

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REFERENCES

1. Pap T, Distler O. Linking angiogenesis to bone destruction in arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2005; 52:1346-8.
2. Smolen JS, Aletaha D, Bijlsma JW, et al. Treating rheumatoid arthritis to target: recommendations of an international task force. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2010;69:631-7.
3. Walther M, Harms H, Krenn V, et al. Correlation of power Doppler sonography with vascularity of the synovial tissue of the knee joint in patients with osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2001; 44:331-8.
4. Szkudlarek M, Court-Payen M, Strandberg C, et al. Power Doppler ultrasonography for assessment of synovitis in the metacarpophalangeal joints of patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a comparison with dynamic magnetic resonance imaging. *Arthritis Rheum* 2001; 44:2018-23.
5. Terslev L, Torp-Pedersen S, Sarnik A, et al. Doppler Ultrasound and Magnetic Resonance Imaging of Synovial Inflammation of the Hand in Rheumatoid Arthritis. A comparative study. *Arthritis Rheum* 2003; 48:2434-41.
6. Naredo E, Bonilla G, Gamero F, et al. Assessment of inflammatory activity in rheumatoid arthritis: a comparative study of clinical evaluation with grey-scale and power Doppler ultrasonography. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2005; 64:375-81.
7. Andersen M, Ellegaard K, Hebsgaard JB, et al. Ultrasound colour Doppler is associated with synovial pathology in biopsies from hand joints in rheumatoid arthritis patients: a cross-sectional study. *Ann Rheum Dis Online First*, published on March 8, 2013.

8. Wakefield RJ, Green MJ, Marzo-Ortega H, et al. Should oligoarthritis be reclassified? Ultrasound reveals a high prevalence of subclinical disease. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2004;63:382-5.
9. Brown AK, Quinn MA, Karim Z, et al. Presence of significant synovitis in rheumatoid arthritis patients with disease-modifying antirheumatic drug-induced clinical remission: evidence from an imaging study may explain structural progression. *Arthritis Rheum* 2006;54:3761-73.
10. Wakefield RJ, Freeston JE, Hensor EM, et al. Delay in imaging versus clinical response: a rationale for prolonged treatment with anti-tumor necrosis factor medication in early rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2007;57:1564-7.
11. Saleem B, Brown AK, Keen H, et al. Disease remission state in patients treated with the combination of tumor necrosis factor blockade and methotrexate or with disease modifying antirheumatic drugs: A clinical and imaging comparative study. *Arthritis Rheum* 2009;60:1915-22.
12. Scire CA, Montecucco C, Codullo V, et al. Ultrasonographic evaluation of joint involvement in early rheumatoid arthritis in clinical remission: power Doppler signal predicts short-term relapse. *Rheumatology* 2009;48:1092-7.
13. Balsa A, de Miguel E, Castillo C, et al. Superiority of SDAI over DAS-28 in assessment of remission in rheumatoid arthritis patients using power Doppler ultrasonography as a gold standard. *Rheumatology* 2010;49:683-90.
14. Saleem B, Brown AK, Keen H, et al. Should imaging be a component of rheumatoid arthritis remission criteria? A comparison between traditional and modified composite remission scores and imaging assessments. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2011;70:792-8.

15. Naredo E, Valor L, De la Torre I, et al. Ultrasound joint inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis in clinical remission: how many and which joints should be assessed? *Arthritis Care Res* 2013;65:512-7.
16. Sakellariou G, Scirè CA, Verstappen SMM, et al. In patients with early rheumatoid arthritis, the new ACR/EULAR definition of remission identifies patients with persistent absence of functional disability and suppression of ultrasonographic synovitis. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2013;72:245-9.
17. Taylor PC, Steuer A, Gruber J, et al. Comparison of Ultrasonographic Assessment of Synovitis and Joint Vascularity with Radiographic Evaluation in a Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Study of Infliximab Therapy in Early Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2004; 50:1107-16.
18. Naredo E, Collado P, Cruz A, et al. Longitudinal power Doppler ultrasonographic assessment of joint inflammatory activity in early rheumatoid arthritis: predictive value in disease activity and radiologic progression. *Arthritis Rheum* 2007; 57: 116-24.
19. Brown AK, Conaghan PG, Karim Z, et al. An Explanation for the Apparent Dissociation Between Clinical Remission and Continued Structural Deterioration in Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2008; 58: 2958-67.
20. Naredo E, Möller I, Cruz A, et al. Power Doppler Ultrasound Monitoring of Response to Anti-Tumor Necrosis Factor Therapy in Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2008; 58: 2248-56.
21. Foltz V, Gandjbakhch F, Etchepare F, et al. Power Doppler Ultrasound, but Not Low-Field Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Predicts Relapse and Radiographic Disease Progression in Rheumatoid Arthritis Patients With Low Levels of Disease Activity. *Arthritis Rheum* 2012;64:67-76.

22. Yoshimi R, Hama M, Takase K, et al. Ultrasonography is a potent tool for the prediction of progressive joint destruction during clinical remission of rheumatoid arthritis. *Mod Rheumatol* 2013;23:456-65.
23. Dougados M, Devauchelle-Pensec V, Ferlet JF, et al. The ability of synovitis to predict structural damage in rheumatoid arthritis: a comparative study between clinical examination and ultrasound. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2013;72:665-671.
24. Peluso G, Michelutti A, Bosello S, et al. Clinical and ultrasonographic remission determines different chances of relapse in early and long standing rheumatoid arthritis. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2011;70:172-5.
25. Saleem B, Brown AJ, Quinn M, et al. Can flare be predicted in DMARD treated RA patients in remission, and is it important? A cohort study. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2012; 71:1316-21.
26. Terslev L, Torp-Pedersen S, Qvistgaard E, et al. Effects of treatment with etanercept (Enbrel, TNRF:Fc) on rheumatoid arthritis evaluated by Doppler ultrasonography. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2003;62:178-81.
27. Fiocco U, Ferro F, Vezzu M, et al. Rheumatoid and psoriatic knee synovitis: clinical, grey scale, and power Doppler ultrasound assessment of the response to etanercept. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2005;64:899-905.
28. Filippucci E, Iagnocco A, Salaffi F, et al. Power Doppler sonography monitoring of synovial perfusion at the wrist joints in patients with rheumatoid arthritis treated with adalimumab. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2006;65:1433-7.
29. Iagnocco A, Filippucci E, Perella C, et al. Clinical and ultrasonographic monitoring of response to adalimumab treatment in rheumatoid arthritis. *J Rheumatol* 2008;35:35-40.

30. Iagnocco A, Perella C, Naredo E, et al. Etanercept in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: clinical follow-up over one year by ultrasonography. *Clin Rheumatol* 2008;27:491-6.
31. Naredo E, Rodríguez M, Campos C, et al. Validity, Reproducibility and Responsiveness of a 12-joint Simplified Power Doppler Ultrasonographic Assessment of Joint Inflammation in Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2008;59:512-22.
32. Ziswiler HR, Aeberli D, Villiger PM, et al. High-resolution ultrasound confirms reduced synovial hyperplasia following rituximab treatment in rheumatoid arthritis. *Rheumatology* 2009;48:939-43.
33. Hammer HB, Sveinsson M, Kongtorp AK, et al. A 78-joints ultrasonographic assessment is associated with clinical assessments and is highly responsive to improvement in a longitudinal study of patients with rheumatoid arthritis starting adalimumab treatment. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2010;69:1349-51.
34. Damjanov N, Radunovic G, Prodanovic S, et al. Construct validity and reliability of ultrasound disease activity score in assessing joint inflammation in RA: comparison with DAS-28. *Rheumatology* 2012;51:184-90.
35. Backhaus TM, Ohrndorf S, Kellner H, et al. The US7 score is sensitive to change in a large cohort of patients with rheumatoid arthritis over 12 months of therapy. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2013;72:1163-9.
36. Iagnocco A, Naredo E, Wakefield R, et al. Responsiveness in Rheumatoid Arthritis. A report from the OMERACT 11 Ultrasound Workshop. *J Rheumatol* 2013 Nov 15.
37. Arnett FC, Edworthy SM, Bloch DA, et al. The American Rheumatism Association 1987 revised criteria for the classification of rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 1988; 31:315-24.

38. Esteve-Vives J, Batlle-Gualda E, Reig A. Spanish version of the Health Assessment Questionnaire: reliability, validity and transcultural equivalency. *J Rheumatol* 1993;20:2116-22.
39. Prevoo ML, van Gestel AM, van 't Hof MA, et al. Remission in a prospective study of patients with rheumatoid arthritis: American Rheumatism Association preliminary remission criteria in relation to the disease activity score. *Br J Rheumatol* 1996;35:1101-5.
40. Aletaha D, Ward MM, Machold KP, et al. Remission and active disease in rheumatoid arthritis: defining criteria for disease activity states. *Arthritis Rheum* 2005;52:2625-36.
41. Wakefield RJ, Balint P, Szkudlarek M, et al. Musculoskeletal Ultrasound Including Definitions for Ultrasonographic Pathology. *J Rheumatol* 2005;32:2485-7.
42. Szkudlarek M, Court-Payen M, Jacobsen S, et al. Interobserver agreement in ultrasonography of the finger and toe joints in rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2003;48:955-62.
43. D'Agostino MA, Conaghan PG, Naredo E, et al. The OMERACT Ultrasound Task Force -- Advances and Priorities. *J Rheumatol* 2009; 36:1829-32.
44. Filippucci E, Farina A, Carotti M, et al. Grey scale and power Doppler sonographic changes induced by intra-articular steroid injection treatment. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2004;63:740-3.
45. Joshua F, de Carle R, Rayment M, et al. Power Doppler 'blanching' after the application of transducer pressure. *Australas Radiol* 2005;49:218-21.
46. Lee V, Zayat A, Wakefield RJ. The effect of joint position on Doppler flow in finger synovitis. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2009;68:603-4.

47. Ellegaard K, Torp-Pedersen S, Henriksen M, et al. Influence of recent exercise and skin temperature on ultrasound Doppler measurements in patients with rheumatoid arthritis—an intervention study. *Rheumatology* 2009;48:1520-3.
48. Semerano L, Gutierrez M, Falgarone G, et al. Diurnal variation of power Doppler in metacarpophalangeal joints of patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a preliminary study. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2011;70:1699-1700.
49. Zayat AS, Conaghan PG, Sharif M, et al. Do non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs have a significant effect on detection and grading of ultrasound-detected synovitis in patients with rheumatoid arthritis? Results from a randomised study. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2011;70:1746-51
50. Ten Cate DF, Luime JJ, Myrthe van der Ven M, et al. Very different performance of the power Doppler modalities of several ultrasound machines ascertained by a microvessel flow phantom. *Arthritis Res Ther* 2013;15:R162.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Longitudinal Doppler ultrasound image of the anterior recess of the humeroradial joint at the elbow that shows B-mode synovitis (s) (grade 2) in a rheumatoid arthritis patient. hc, humeral capitellum; rh, radial head.

Figure 2. Longitudinal Doppler ultrasound image of the dorsal aspect of a metacarpophalangeal joint that shows B-mode synovitis (grade 2) and Doppler synovitis (grade 3) in a rheumatoid arthritis patient. mc, metacarpal bone; pp, proximal phalanx.

TABLES

Table 1. Assessment time points for each subcutaneous anti-TNF

Anti-TNF	Assessment time point at peak plasma concentration	Assessment time point at trough plasma concentration
Adalimumab	Day 4-6 after administration	Day 13 after administration
Certolizumab	Day 3-7 after administration	Day 13 after administration
Etanercept	Day 2-3 after administration	Day 6 after administration
Golimumab	Day 2-6 after administration	Day 27 after administration

Table 2. Clinical, laboratory, and B-mode and Doppler US parameters and differences between them at peak time and trough time assessments

Parameters	Mean (SD) (range) values at peak time	Mean (SD) (range) values at trough time	Diff (95% CI)	p values
DAS28	2.22 (0.95) (0.49-4.6)	2.22 (1.03) (0.49-4.76)	0.00 (-0.13-0.13)	0.986
SDAI	6.20 (4.51) (0.1-20)	6.56 (4.53) (0.1-21.1)	-0.36 (-1.15-0.42)	0.356
TJC (0-28)	1.80 (2.88) (0-14)	1.65 (2.59) (0-14)	0.14 (-0.23-0.52)	0.448
SJC (0-28)	0.31 (0.77) (0-4)	0.43 (0.87) (0-4)	-0.12 (-0.29-0.05)	0.159
VAS by patient (0-10)	3.80 (2.17) (0-10)	4.08 (2.13) (0-10)	-0.29 (-0.75-0.18)	0.227
VAS by doctor (0-10)	1.73 (1.13) (0-5)	1.82 (1.11) (0-5)	-0.08 (-0.25-0.08)	0.322
ESR (mm/1 st h)	13.49 (9.85) (2-48)	13.53 (10.91) (2-52)	-0.04 (-1.43-1.35)	0.953
CRP (mg/dL)	0.30 (0.27) (0.1-1.1)	0.40 (0.62) (0.1-3.9)	-0.10 (-0.23-0.03)	0.130
HAQ (0-3)	0.21 (0.36) (0-1)	0.21 (0.36) (0-1)	NA	NA
BSI-12 joints (0-36)	4.33 (4.39) (0-21)	4.45 (3.89) (0-19)	-0.12 (-0.66-0.41)	0.648
BSC-12 joints (0-12)	2.96 (2.41) (0-10)	3.22 (2.28) (0-9)	-0.27 (-0.70-0.17)	0.225
DSI-12 joints (0-36)	1.33 (2.34) (0-7)	1.55 (2.33) (0-10)	-0.22 (-0.69-0.24)	0.338
DSC-12 joints (0-12)	0.59 (1.04) (0-3)	0.76 (1.13) (0-4)	-0.16 (-0.38-0.05)	0.132
BSI-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-60)	5.63 (4.22) (0-16)	5.12 (4.16) (0-15)	0.51 (-0.30-1.32)	0.213
BSC-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-20)	3.80 (2.81) (0-13)	3.73 (2.71) (0-9)	0.06 (-0.57-0.69)	0.846
DSI-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-60)	1.22 (2.28) (0-8)	1.49 (2.75) (0-12)	-0.27 (-0.96-0.43)	0.444
DSC-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-20)	0.57 (1.06) (0-4)	0.71 (1.29) (0-6)	-0.14 (-0.47-0.19)	0.391

DAS28, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints; SDAI, Simplified Disease Activity Index; TCJ, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; VAS, visual analog scale for overall disease activity; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP, C-reactive protein; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; BSI, B-mode synovitis index; BSC, B-mode synovitis count; DSI, Doppler synovitis index; DSC, Doppler synovitis count; W-MCP-A-MTP, wrists-metacarpophalangeal joints-ankles-metatarsophalangeal joints; Diff, values at peak time-values at trough time; NA, not applicable

Table 3. Patients with active disease and patients in remission according to clinical and US criteria at peak time and trough time assessments

Criteria	Activity at peak time n (%) of patients	Remission at peak time n (%) of patients	Activity at trough time n (%) of patients	Remission at trough time n (%) of patients	p values
DAS28	16 (32.7)	33 (67.3)	16 (32.7)	33 (67.3)	1.000
SDAI	30 (61.2)	19 (38.8)	34 (69.4)	15 (30.6)	0.344
B-mode US 12-joints	40 (81.6)	9 (18.4)	44 (89.8)	5 (10.2)	0.219
Doppler US 12-joints	14 (28.6)	35 (71.4)	20 (40.8)	29 (59.2)	0.070
B-mode US W-MCP-A-MTP	44 (89.8)	5 (10.2)	43 (87.8)	6 (12.2)	1.000

Doppler US 14 (28.6) 35 (71.4) 18 (36.7) 31 (63.32) 0.388
W-MCP-A-MTP

DAS28, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints; SDAI, Simplified Disease Activity Index; US, ultrasound; W-MCP-A-MTP, wrists-metacarpophalangeal joints-ankles-metatarsophalangeal joints; n, number

Table 4. Patients with higher, equal and lower values of clinical, laboratory and B-mode and Doppler US parameters at the assessment time points

Parameters	Peak time value–trough	Peak time value–trough	Peak time value–trough
	time value < 0 n (%) of patients	time value = 0 n (%) of patients	time value > 0 n (%) of patients
DAS28	28 (57.1)	3 (6.1)	18 (36.7)
SDAI	24 (49.0)	9 (18.4)	16 (32.7)
TJC (0-28)	10 (20.4)	27 (55.1)	12 (24.5)
SJC (0-28)	5 (10.2)	42 (85.7)	2 (4.1)
VAS by patient (0-10)	18 (36.7)	22 (44.9)	9 (18.4)
VAS by doctor (0-10)	9 (18.4)	36 (73.5)	4 (8.2)
ESR (mm/1 st h)	23 (46.9)	8 (16.3)	18 (36.7)
CRP (mg/dL)	15 (30.6)	25 (51.0)	9 (18.4)
HAQ (0-3)	0 (0.0)	49 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
BSI-12 joints (0-36)	21 (42.9)	11 (22.4)	17 (34.7)
BSC-12 joints (0-12)	22 (44.9)	12 (24.5)	15 (30.6)
DSI-12 joints (0-36)	10 (20.4)	33 (67.3)	6 (12.2)
DSC-12 joints (0-12)	10 (20.4)	35 (71.4)	4 (8.2)
BSI-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-60)	21 (42.9)	5 (10.2)	23 (46.9)
BSC-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-20)	19 (38.8)	13 (26.5)	17 (34.7)
DSI-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-60)	10 (20.4)	31 (63.3)	8 (16.3)
DSC-W-MCP-A-MTP (0-20)	9 (18.4)	33 (67.3)	7 (14.3)

DAS28, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints; SDAI, Simplified Disease Activity Index; TCJ, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; VAS, visual analog scale for overall disease activity; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP, C-reactive protein; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; BSI, B-mode synovitis index; BSC, B-mode synovitis count; DSI, Doppler synovitis index; DSC, Doppler synovitis count; W-MCP-A-MTP, wrists-metacarpophalangeal joints-ankles-metatarsophalangeal joints; n, number